

1º The thee focus-groups conducted

Between October 2021 and January 2022, three focus groups were organized with the participation of 18 experts from small companies in Castellón, Valencia and Alicante (see images 1-3). During these dynamics, participants shared their knowledge about aspects such as: the main barriers in the transition to the circular economy, the circular measures they have already implemented in their companies, responsible selection of suppliers, and the importance of communication to citizens and training among their employees (Figure 1 and 2). The aim of the focus groups was to identify challenges and needs in relation to the transition to the circular economy of companies in the tourism sector (hotels and restaurants) in the Valencian Community.

Image 1. Experts from small companies in Castellón. Focus group held at the UNIVERSITAT JAUME I in December 2021.

Image 2. Experts from small companies in Alicante. Focus group held at the UNIVERSITAT D'ALACANT in December 2021.

Image 3. Experts from small companies in Valencia. Focus group held at the UNIVERSITAT DE VALÈNCIA in January 2022.

Figure 1. Topics addressed during the dynamics.

The main results are included in the **REPORT ON THE NEEDS OF THE TOURISM SECTOR FOR THE TRANSITION TO A CIRCULAR ECONOMY** (Figure 3) available on the project website and in Zenodo

<https://innoecotur.webs.upv.es/primer-informe-de-necesidades-del-sector-turistico-para-la-transicion-a-la-economia-circular/>

10.5281/zenodo.6325273

Figure 2. Barriers to the implementation of the circular economy identified in the three focus groups.

2. LA ECONOMÍA CIRCULAR

La Estrategia de Economía Circular en España (MITECO, 2020) toma como referencia sectores incluidos en la Tabla 3, entre los que se encuentra el sector del turismo, por su importancia en la economía española.

Tabla 3. Sectores prioritarios en la Estrategia de Economía Circular 2030 de España

Sector	Causa	Economía circular, Ej
Construcción	Genera el 40% de los residuos y emite el 20% de los gases de efecto invernadero.	- Gestión de los residuos, incluir separación y clasificación. - Aumento del reciclaje y reutilización.
Agricultura, ganadería, silvicultura y pesca	Desperdicio de recursos naturales como el agua y desperdicio alimentario.	- Reducir el desperdicio alimentario. - Valoración de alimentos de subproductos para alimentación.
Industria	La industria manufacturera genera el 17% de los residuos. Desperdicio alimentario en el sector HORECA.	- Uso de tecnologías que fomenten el aprovechamiento de los recursos. - Reducción de desperdicios.
Bienes de consumo	La vida útil de los bienes de consumo se ha reducido.	- Reducir los residuos generados por la industria. - Fomentar el uso de productos duraderos y reparables. - Reutilización de productos.
Turismo	Uso intensivo del recurso hídrico, elevada generación de residuos.	- Reducir los residuos generados por la industria. - Fomentar el uso de productos duraderos y reparables. - Reutilización de productos.
Textil y confección	Entre el 26-70% del impacto ambiental del consumo, entre los países que desecha más cantidad de ropa.	- Reciclado separado de otros residuos. - Gestión del residuo textil.

Fuente: MITECO (2020)

2022 Informe de necesidades del sector turístico para la transición a la economía circular

Universitat Politècnica De València Proyecto INNOECOTUR

2022 Informe de necesidades del sector turístico para la transición a la economía circular

Lugar: Los focus tuvieron lugar en Alicante, Castellón y Valencia uno en cada provincia de la Comunidad Valenciana.

- ALICANTE:** Se realizó en la sede de la Universidad de Alicante. Profesores del Departamento de Organización de Empresas de esta universidad moderaron el primer focus group y seleccionaron a los participantes.
- CASTELLÓN:** Se realizó en la sede de la Universitat Jaume I. Profesores del Departamento de Administración de Empresas y Marketing de esta universidad moderaron el segundo focus group y seleccionaron a los participantes.
- VALENCIA:** Se realizó en la sede de la Universitat Politècnica de València. Profesores del Departamento de Dirección de Empresas de la Universidad de Valencia moderaron el tercer focus group y seleccionaron a los participantes.

Focus group 1	Focus group 2	Focus group 3
Alicante	Castellón	Valencia
6	6	6
30-50 años	30-50 años	30-50 años
2	2	2
2	2	2
1	1	1
1	1	1

EL PROYECTO INNOECOTUR

Las transcripciones de las entrevistas se encuentran en la guía que sirvió de acciones. Se de interés a los participantes:

En la guía de la economía circular se encuentran los materiales para una empresa innovadora. Se de interés a los participantes.

En un orden secuencial se le entregó el material al moderador siguiendo el orden y marcado por los participantes.

Las transcripciones de las entrevistas se encuentran en la guía que sirvió de acciones. Se de interés a los participantes.

Figure 3. Report on the needs of the tourism sector for the transition to a circular economy.

2^o Team (UV)

VNIVERSITAT VALÈNCIA

The Innoecotur project team, coordinated by the Universitat Politècnica de Valencia, is made up of members of the University of Alicante, the Universitat Jaume I, the Universitat de València and Invat.tur, with the collaboration of the University of Malaga Faculty of Tourism, the University of Castilla La Mancha, the University of Seville, FOTUR, APEHA, VISIT BENIDORM and GRUPO INTUR.

In the case of the University of Valencia (UV), the team consists of a coordinator and three collaborators, who actively participate in InnoEcoTur.

UV has a long tradition and strong involvement with the Circular Economy. In its mission statement, vision and values, it advocates being at the service of ecological and environmental defense, through various programs such as the Sustainable Campus. Through its research structures such as Research Groups and Chairs, it also supports and promotes activities framed within the Circular Economy, with different objectives such as a better use of water, the analysis of the economic, social and environmental viability of projects, as well as the sustainability of the main industrial practices implemented.

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Guillermo Navarro-Sanfeliu

PhD in Business Management from the Universitat de València. Expert in entrepreneurship, business models and SMEs. Member of the Research Group GESTOR Research Group (Organizational Geostrategy: Clusters and Competitiveness).
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Partners

Collaborators

3º Next Event

1st Workshop on Circular Economy Strategy and Action Plans in the Tourism Sector

On June 3, 2022 the **1st Workshop on Circular Economy Strategy and Action Plans in the Tourism Sector** will take place in Valencia. It will be held by the Universitat Politècnica de València, in collaboration with the Universitat de València, the University of Alicante, the Universitat Jaume I and Invat.tur. During the workshop, the first results and achievements of the project “**Creation of an Innovation Platform for the Promotion and Implementation of a Circular Economy Strategy in the Tourism Sector of the Valencian Community**” will be presented. This project is led by Full Professor Marival Segarra Oña at Universitat Politècnica de València. It was subsidized in the 2021 call for complementary actions to promote and strengthen innovation of the Agència Valenciana de la Innovació (AVI). The aim of this program is to strengthen the existing innovation support structures in the Valencian Community and to facilitate the dissemination of R&D&I among companies.

The purpose of this initial workshop will be to present the initiative and its results, to generate a wide dissemination of technological, eco-innovative results, R+D+i methodologies and documents of interest to the Tourism Sector of the Valencian

Community, with the aim of linking the economic, social and environmental impacts with the Sustainable Development Goals (Figure 4). The first workshop will contribute to inclusive participation and the generation of multi-stakeholder dialogues, bringing together researchers, policy makers and industry.

I Workshop Innoecotur

Figure 4. SDG6, SDG7, SDG 11, SDG12, SDG13, SDG14, SDG13 y SDG 15, related to InnoEcoTur Project.

The workshop program will be divided into three blocks (Figure 5). The first block will offer an analysis of the circular economy's current situation in the tourism sector, from the perspective of researchers and policy makers. The second block will aim to promote the design/redesign of processes and products, driving the development and application of new knowledge and technologies to promote innovation in processes, products, services and business models, fostering public-private collaboration.

Finally, the third block will be aimed at encouraging the involvement of economic and social agents in general, and citizens in particular, to raise awareness of current environmental, economic and technological challenges.

Figure 5. Contents of the program of the 1st Workshop on Circular Economy Strategy and Action Plans in the Tourism Sector.

More information at

<https://innoecotur.webs.upv.es/jornadas-innoecotur/>

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